

RISK MANAGEMENT IN OPEN BANKING

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Abstract

Modern fintech technologies are one of the biggest innovations in the banking sector in recent years. Rapid digitalization and technological progress in the banking sector have pushed the traditional banking model into the background and put an open banking system, which is an open and innovative structure. This article examines the evolution of open banking in the financial sector, as well as the risks and opportunities associated with this change. The introduction to the article highlights the purpose and importance of the research, focusing on the transformation process in the banking sector and the definition of open banking. In the research method, the current state and future potential of open banking are assessed by analyzing data obtained using methods such as a review of current literature, selection of sources, surveys and interviews¹. One of the main sections of the article is devoted to the main differences between the closed banking model and the open banking system. The basic principles of traditional and open banking are considered in detail. This chapter sheds light on fundamental changes in the industry, with a particular focus on changes in the technology infrastructure. Another important part of the study focused on the risks associated with open banking. Data security and privacy issues, legal challenges, competition, and

¹ September 2014, “Data Sharing and Open Data for Banks: A report for HM Treasury and Cabinet Office”

innovation risks will be discussed in detail in this section. On the other hand, the opportunities offered by an open bank are also discussed in a separate section. Issues such as improving the customer experience, diversity of financial products, and expanding innovation opportunities highlight the positive changes in the sector. The Results and Discussions section compares closed and open banking models². In addition, there are suggestions for reducing risks and evaluating opportunities. The Solutions section of the article covers practical solutions, such as security strategies in open banking applications, regulatory development, and training of banking personnel. The literature section presents the main sources of open banking, literature on changes in the banking sector, and current research on risk and opportunity analysis.

Key words:

Open Banking, Embedded finance, Digitalization, Financial Innovation, Security Risks, Financial Transformation.

Introduction

Today, digitalization and modern fintech technologies in the banking sector are progressing. One of the key players in this transformation, Open Bank aims to make financial services more transparent, accessible and innovative by radically changing traditional banking models. The transition from the traditional banking model to open banking creates unique risks and opportunities in the financial sector. In this article, we will discuss in detail the key differences, risks, and opportunities between a traditional bank and an open bank to understand these changes that are driving the evolution of the financial world.

For many years, the banking sector existed in a traditional structure, and the

². “The views expressed in the article are the authors personal opinions and not representative of the World Bank's management or board of Directors.”

interaction between the client and the bank was carried out using limited and standardized operations. However, with the digitization of the banking sector, customers began to have more opportunities. An open banking system offers an ecosystem where financial information and services are provided openly, and customers can securely share their financial information. The development of an open bank is closely linked to such dynamics as the widespread introduction of digital technologies, changing customer requirements and promoting competition to a global level. While the traditional banking model has a limited understanding of the financial situation of customers, an open bank aims to create more complete financial accessibility by integrating customer information.

The benefits of an open bank include radically improving the quality of customer service and enabling faster development and delivery of financial products. While customers can manage their finances more efficiently with an open bank, banks can gain a competitive advantage by offering customer-specific solutions. One of the main problems of an open bank is ensuring data security and confidentiality.

The digital Bank has expanded the boundaries of financial services, providing customers with 24/7 access and the convenience of making a number of financial transactions through mobile applications. Thus, it was possible to provide personalized services that can instantly meet the financial needs of customers. An important element of changes in the banking sector is data analysis and the use of artificial intelligence technologies. By analyzing large amounts of data, banks gain a great advantage in understanding customer behavior, assessing credit risk, and strengthening security measures. This not only helps to increase customer satisfaction, but also allows you to manage your financial processes more efficiently³.

³ Adapted from, “Regulatory Approaches to Open Banking”, World Bank, 2020.

In addition, the growth in the number of fintech companies has begun to cause various types of competition in the banking sector. These companies gain customer loyalty by offering innovative solutions compared to traditional banks, especially in areas such as payment systems, credit assessment and investment management. In this competitive environment, banks need to make faster decisions, increase flexibility, and develop customer-focused strategies. Digitalization and technological transformation have affected not only the customer service and operational processes of banks, but also their product and service portfolios. Cryptocurrencies, blockchain technology and other innovative financial instruments have led to the diversification of the industry, providing alternative solutions to traditional banking models.

However, this transformation process also carries some risks. Factors such as cybersecurity threats, data privacy concerns, and regulatory complexity can prevent banks from successfully managing this new financial paradigm. Changes in the banking sector are aimed at increasing innovation, collaboration and sustainability in the future. Banks must be constantly updated to respond quickly to customer requests, closely monitor technological developments, and build a robust digital infrastructure.

The transformation of the banking sector is fundamentally changing financial services, and the consequences of this transformation process are leading to changes in the sector not only from a technological point of view, but also from the point of view of the business model, customer experience and competition dynamics. The future of banking will evolve towards a fast, reliable and customer-oriented structure integrated with technology, and this process will open up new opportunities and challenges for all stakeholders in the sector. Open banking is a concept that aims to make the provision of financial services more transparent,

accessible and innovative by radically changing traditional banking models⁴.

The banking sector is developing rapidly today. One of the most important things about these changes is the fundamental differences between a closed and open bank. The purpose of this article is to understand how these two approaches have evolved and their impact on the financial sector by comparing closed and open banking models. The fundamental differences between traditional and open banking models are one of the important factors determining the future of financial services. The transition from the traditional structure of the banking model to an open banking model has led to significant changes in the technological infrastructure. These changes point to a financial future that aims to provide customers with more choice, competition, and personalized services.

Risks associated with an open bank⁵

Although open banking is a revolutionary change in the financial sector, it carries with it a number of potential risks. This article focuses on the risks associated with an open bank and discusses various aspects of understanding these risks.

Regulatory risks should not be ignored. Any innovation in the financial sector attracts the attention of regulators, who raise various compliance issues. Open banking is a big risk in this area, as it must comply with different regulations in different countries. Adapting to different legal frameworks can be a complex process for financial institutions⁶.

⁴ World Bank, Open Banking Regulatory Approaches - Technical Study on Regulatory Approaches for Open Banking

⁵ World Bank.

⁶ Khoshimov PhD, E., and F. Makhmudaliev. "Digital transformation of corporate governance in Uzbekistan: current state, challenges and perspectives." *International Finance and Accounting* 2020.6 (2020): 30.

Technological risks should also be included in the open banking risk profile. Sharing data via the API increases the risk of technical errors, system crashes, and malware attacks. In addition, vulnerabilities in security protocols can allow the use of technological infrastructure, which can lead to a violation of the integrity of the system. Customers may be concerned about the security of their financial information, and this requires financial institutions to be vigilant in ensuring customer satisfaction and trust. While an open bank offers customers greater control and transparency, there is also a risk of abuse of this control.

Operational risks are another category of risks that arise due to the complexity of business processes in an open banking ecosystem. Operational challenges such as integration between different financial institutions, regulating the flow of data, and responding quickly to customer requests can increase the operational risk of an open bank. This creates a complex environment in which financial institutions must manage effectively.

The open banking model is based on the ability to exchange customer information. However, it is very important that data is transferred and stored securely during the exchange process. Data transmission via an open API must be protected from malicious attacks and comply with industry-standard security protocols. In this way, the confidentiality and integrity of the client's data can be protected. The legal and regulatory challenges of an open banking model can also affect customer confidence. Customers want to make sure that their data is protected and processed in accordance with legal regulations. Financial institutions should be transparent in this regard and convince their clients to comply with the rules.

Opportunities provided by the open bank⁷

One of the most important characteristics of an open bank is positive changes

⁷ World Bank, Fintech and the Future of Finance, 2022.

in the customer experience. Providing clients with more choice and flexibility between different financial service providers allows them to make more customized decisions according to individual needs. This helps clients manage their financial services more effectively and achieve their personal financial goals.

An open bank promotes innovation by facilitating the integration of fintech companies and other third parties into the financial ecosystem. This allows financial institutions to diversify and improve the services they provide to their customers. The introduction of innovative products and services will increase competition and provide consumers with a more diverse choice.

An open bank provides greater integration and aggregation of financial products and services. This gives customers the opportunity to meet their various financial needs in one place, through an app or platform. For example, a customer can track credit card transactions, manage different bank accounts, and track their investment portfolio using the same app. An open bank increases competition in the financial sector and provides customers with more affordable and transparent services. Financial institutions may be asked to offer competitive interest rates, lower fees, and more profitable financial products to retain or attract customers. This has a positive effect on providing consumers with economic benefits. This improved customer experience allows financial institutions to establish closer ties with their customers and develop long-term relationships. In addition, increasing customer loyalty increases the likelihood that customers will keep their financial products and services in the same organization. This opens the way for financial institutions to build a stable customer base.

An open bank makes it easier for entrepreneurs to do business in the field of financial technology. With access to customer information, fintech companies can offer more customized solutions and implement innovative projects that change traditional banking models. This increases competition in the industry and opens up more options for consumers to choose from.

Research method⁸

The research method refers to the systematic approach that underlies the research and is chosen to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the information obtained. In this article, titled "Research method", we explain subheadings in detail, such as literature review and source selection, methods of data collection and analysis, surveys and interviews about the current state of open banking.

The literature review and selection of sources underlying the study include the steps of identifying available information on the topic, reviewing previous studies, and collecting data from similar studies. The study of the available literature on the economic and financial consequences of open banking forms the knowledge base for this article and provides the research with a solid theoretical foundation.

Selecting sources includes selecting articles, reports, and books that are trustworthy and academic in nature. This is important to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the data that forms the basis of the study. A review of the literature is also important for understanding current developments, applications, and problems in open banking. (Roche, J. C., & Tirole, J. 1996)

Result and discussion⁹

The purpose of this article is to discuss changes in the financial sector, compare traditional and open banking models, assess the future and expectations of an open bank, and consider ways to reduce risks and assess opportunities. It is important to note the main differences between traditional and open banking models. While a traditional bank is characterized by strict rules and a generally closed structure, an open bank offers a more flexible, customer-centric model that encourages data sharing. With the introduction of open banking services, cooperation between financial institutions is expanding, offering customers a wider

⁸ Adapted from World Bank, Fintech and the Future of Finance, 2022.

⁹ Adapted from "Role of consumer consent in open banking", World Bank, 2021.

range of services. However, you also need to consider the security and legal issues that arise when implementing this model.

The future of open banking is determined by rapidly changing technologies and customer preferences. Elements such as technological developments, digitization, and artificial intelligence open up new opportunities for financial services delivery. In the future of open banking, while more financial institutions are expected to adopt this model, regulators will also have to monitor and monitor the process. In this context, it is expected that as digitalization accelerates, the open bank will strengthen its role in the financial sector.

The introduction of open banking services involves various risks. Concerns about security, data privacy, and regulatory uncertainty are driving financial institutions to exercise caution. To mitigate these risks, it is important to establish industry standards and guidelines, implement strong security protocols, and ensure effective interaction with regulators. On the other hand, despite the risks that arise from this transformation, an open bank also opens up great opportunities for financial institutions. Opportunities such as increased customer satisfaction, rapid innovation, access to a broad customer base, and competitive advantage are among the advantages that can be achieved through the introduction of open banking services¹⁰.

¹⁰ Baxodir o‘g J. J. et al. O ‘zbekiston iqtisodiyotining raqamli transformatsiyasida P2P biznes modellarining o ‘rni //MOLIYA VA BANK ISHI. – 2022. – T. 8. – №.

Consent Management and right to be forgotten: Any information exchange via APIs between entities will need the data subject's express consent. For instance, consent must be provided freely, voluntarily, and with specified intent, according to Québec's Protection of Personal Information in the Private Sector. It must be asked for for each of these reasons, in plain language, and apart from any other information that is given to the individual in question. We anticipate that the federal rules will follow suit, meaning that obtaining authorization is a crucial component of any open banking plan that permits an company to use APIs.

In actuality, consent and how it is managed are frequently undervalued. Fintechs are being considered by several businesses as a means of managing consent. Data subjects now have an extra "right to be forgotten" under new privacy regulations, therefore businesses need to make sure they have the procedures in place to comply with this request from a data subject and that other third parties follow suit. Maintaining consent, withholding consent, and disclosing all personal information are still the data controller's responsibilities. A person or entity that oversees data processing and is in charge of adhering to data protection laws is known as the data controller.

Data management: To guarantee that the data controller can show they comprehend how data travels across various business processes and enabling technological components, as well as who has access to it, the data flow should be operationally mapped from beginning to finish.

Throughout the data lifecycle, agreements should be made about the identification, classification, protection, retention, and destruction of client records by the organization's data controller, data processor, and/or any third parties involved in any capacity. A person or entity that handles personal data under the direction of a controller for particular needs and services provided to the controller is known as a data processor.

Policies controlling the classification, degree of security, retention, and

deletion of client information should be developed with regulatory obligations front and center. Furthermore, as more businesses use AI, machine learning, and sophisticated analytics engines to extract insights from their data, they need also be aware of the concerns related to data ethics and quality.

Data portability is another important factor that enterprises should think about. To what extent may your company relocate the data at the request of the data subject? How much speed could you achieve? Have you incorporated all of these safeguards into your open banking plan?

Security risk: Another consideration will be the procedure for handling events or data breaches. In a world where protecting IT systems is now essential and required for all types of businesses, it's critical to be ready to defend against cyberattacks in the most economical manner possible. Organizations should think about how the API design affects their security strategy in addition to responding to cybersecurity threats. Furthermore, authorities are closely monitoring the evolution of cyberthreats. For instance, the major focus of Draft Guideline B-13, Technology and Cyber Risk Management, released by the Office of the Superintendent of Financial Institutions (OSFI) is cybersecurity and risk management. Because of the changing economic and regulatory environment as well as the rise in cyberthreats, businesses must adopt a proactive risk-reduction strategy. Businesses can use best practices from the industry to create security resilience strategies that address particular risks that might affect their operations.

Business risk: As the post-pandemic industry takes shape, consumer expectations are changing. Increased use of technology and the ready availability of information means that consumers’ knowledge around their rights, privacy and

2021 usage vs. 2024 preference and net % change ● 2021 ● by 2024 ● Net % change

Clients indicating their changing financial provider relationships
 Note: % change figures may differ due to rounding; figures are for % of clients

data use is growing. Banks can no longer afford not to meet their customers’ expectations and needs with regards to the speed at which they want information, flexibility of product offerings, transparency around how their data is being used and with whom their data is shared.

Over and above increasing investments in technology, organizations need to establish practices to govern their data stewardship, ethics, transparency, privacy and protection to demonstrate their commitment to their customers. Adoption of hybrid consumer engagement models, employee training and use of AI and deep learning technology are other considerations organizations should thoroughly evaluate when considering an open banking environment.

Third-party risk: Organizations have historically used outside parties to support an ideal distribution of new functions and to improve scalability and

availability. We believe that as open banking becomes more prevalent, businesses will collaborate more with fintechs and other outside parties to provide fresh goods and services. Businesses will encounter never-before-seen demands about the pace at which they must cultivate relationships—some of which are only API users—in third-party risk management procedures and technology.

The interconnected landscape of today’s business environment and the inevitable increase in third-party interaction in the open banking environment pose a serious risk of disruption to current processes and risk appetite that could result in significant loss of revenue. Organizations need to evaluate the ability of their critical offshore presence and third parties to continuously support critical functions such as IT, human resources, payroll, financial reporting, cybersecurity and others.

Table 1: Risk Types and Descriptions

Risk Type	Description
Cybersecurity Risks	Increased exposure to cyberattacks and vulnerabilities due to greater connectivity

Data Privacy Risks	Risks related to compliance with data protection regulations and prevention of data breaches
Third-Party Risks	Risks arising from collaborations with third-party providers with varying security protocols
Operational Risks	Operational challenges such as system downtimes, integration failures, and poor API quality
Regulatory Risks	Risks associated with non-compliance to varying regional and international regulations
Reputational Risks	Damage to reputation from service interruptions, breaches, and poor management

Table 2: Suggestions for Risk Management

Suggestion	Description
Enhance Cybersecurity Infrastructure	Invest in multi-factor authentication, encryption, and continuous monitoring
Strengthen Regulatory Compliance Frameworks	Maintain robust compliance with evolving regulations on data and financial security
Implement Comprehensive Third-Party Risk Management	Conduct due diligence on third parties and establish regular audits
Develop a Risk Culture Within the Organization	Foster awareness and training about risk management across all organizational levels

Enhance Operational Resilience	Establish resilient systems and contingency plans to manage operational risks
Collaborate on Industry-Wide Standards	Work with regulatory bodies to establish consistent standards for open banking
Customer Education and Awareness	Educate customers on data sharing practices and risk mitigation strategies

Pie Chart: Risk Distribution in Open Banking

The pie chart above represents the distribution of various risks in open banking, with cybersecurity, data privacy, and regulatory risks taking a significant portion of the overall risk profile.

Conclusions and suggestions

This article covers security strategies, regulatory development, and training and qualification of bank employees in the field of open banking applications. These elements are critical to ensuring the security of the open banking ecosystem, supporting effective enforcement of regulations, and ensuring that financial institutions thrive under this new model¹¹.

Customers' changing needs are driving financial institutions to modernize their products and how they serve their customers. As more financial institutions consider open banking, regulations are being enforced worldwide to support innovation while retaining strong risk management and governance principles. Integrating robust security, data, privacy and third-party risk management

¹¹ BIS, "API Standards for Data Sharing", 2022

principles as a part of innovation strategy can enable financial institutions to realize the benefits of transformation.

Open banking also poses new security challenges with elements such as sharing data with customers and integrating digital services. This is why financial institutions should develop and implement secure security strategies. These strategies should include industry-standard encryption methods and use secure APIs and authentication mechanisms. In addition, measures should be taken such as rapid response to potential security breaches and the establishment of permanent security monitoring systems.

An open bank requires financial regulators to create more effective and comprehensive regulatory documents. This is important both to ensure the protection of customer data and to promote fair competition in the industry. Regulators should establish a strong framework for oversight of open banking programs and strict oversight of organizations working in this area. This framework should include data security standards, customer privacy rules, and a comprehensive approach to auditing open banking platforms.

An open bank requires employees of financial institutions to adapt to new technologies and business models. In this regard, the training and qualification of bank employees plays an important role. The financial sector should organize training programs and internal training to train professionals with digital skills. This allows you to effectively manage open banking programs, and also helps industry professionals maintain a competitive advantage. We can make the following suggestions¹²:

1) Open Banking improvements:

- new requirements for dedicated data access interfaces
- banks will no longer need to maintain two data access interfaces

¹² Included by the author

- open banking providers to be given contingency hashtag#data access (to secure business continuity in case the primary bank interface is down)
- all providers (banks and PSPs) to set up a “dashboard” for consumers to view, control (and be able to revoke) data access rights
- obligation to provide access to financial data beyond payment account data

2) Fraud mitigation:

- extend refund rights for fraud victims
- new mandatory system to match IBAN numbers with account names
- stronger customer authentication rules
- a legal basis for PSPs to share fraud-related information between them

3) Fairer competition between banks and the 1000+ non-bank PSPs to drive down prices:

- allow PSPs to access all EU payment systems
- secure payment and e-money institutions’ (there are 800 and 270 respectively) access to a bank account

4) Simplification:

- merging e-money institutions (EMIs) with payment institutions (PIs) under one regime
- all payment rules applicable to PSPs will be contained in a directly applicable regulation

5) Improve the availability of cash in shops and via ATMs, by allowing retailers to provide cash services to customers without requiring a purchase and clarifying the rules for independent ATM operators

6) Improve consumer rights (i.e. when funds are blocked, improve transparency on account statements and ATM charges)

It’s important to note that on top of PSD3 the above will be implemented by a Payment Services Regulation (PSR). The difference is that the former (PSD3) needs

to be transposed into the national laws of all EU Member States, whereas the latter (PSR) is an EU Regulation, which will apply directly across all member states once adopted without the need for any additional local implementation.

To ensure successful management of these changes in the financial sector, open banking programs must take into account security strategies, regulatory development, and the training and qualifications of banking personnel in general. Effective integration of these elements will be an important step towards increasing customer confidence, while ensuring the best use of open banking opportunities.

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